

PROCESSES OF DRAWING UP A VENTILATION SYSTEM SCHEME IN MINES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620847>

Abstract. Ventilation is a fundamental part of any underground mine operations. The main purpose of underground ventilation is to provide sufficient air to all workplaces. Today, modern mechanized underground metal mines are widely used mobile equipment powered by diesel fuel. production rates. Ore can be obtained from many productions due to the production rate at the mine will stop. Amount of air flow the demand for an underground mine depends on several factors, including daily production capacity, number of diesel equipment, ambient temperature, extraction method, extraction depth and airway type. After the implementation of IV stage emission standards for non-road diesel engines, this is becoming more difficult to determine hence the amount of air flow required for underground mines reducing diesel emissions. The amount of air flow required for the mine is taken up by the ventilation fans and is the biggest cost aspect in the mine ventilation - power consumption to operate ventilation fans this can reach up to 50 percent of the mine's total electricity power cost. The price of electricity has increased has increased significantly in recent years and may continue to increase The future. Therefore, identification becomes more important proper ventilation design for underground metal mines.

Keywords: Mine ventilation, ventilation control, mechanized mining, ventilation on demand, optimized model-based control, minimal energy consumption, advanced process control, air quality, ventilation efficiency.

Introduction

Ventilation can be described as the lifeblood of the mine, the recipient airways act like arteries, carrying oxygen there working areas of the mine and return, working as veins, pollutants are transported away from the working areas of the mines, must be released into the atmosphere. Ventilation fresh, cool air flow to the mine's underground workings to dilute and remove dust and harmful gases (usually NO_x, SO₂, methane, CO₂ and CO) and to regulate temperature. The main purpose of the underground ventilation system provide fresh air in sufficient

quantity and quality for dilution to safe concentrations of pollutants in all parts of the mine should be installed in places where the work of employees is required. Fresh air enters the mine through the surface the ventilation shaft is raised or distributed through the adit and then Internal ventilation rises and mine by ramps. Currents controlled by regulators and permanently installed ventilation . The auxiliary ventilation system takes air from the main air flows and distributes through mining operations temporarily installed ventilation fans and spiral ducts. Air always flows along the path of least resistance, but it may not it must be where it is needed for use. Where to direct the air air handling devices are used if necessary. There are two main ones categories: active devices that add energy to direct air where necessary or passive devices that add resistance flow paths to assist air flow along other paths (Picture 1). Active devices include main fans and amplifiers. Passive devices include air doors, regulators, air passages, stops and seals. The main means of production of fans and ventilation air flow control. Main fans (solo or combination) provides all the air that has passed through the mine and is available usually located on or near the surface. The most two The fans most commonly used in mine ventilation are centrifugal fans and axial fans, although in some cases mixed-flow fans used.

Picture 1. Components of mine ventilation system

Mine ventilation systems must not only ensure health and the safety of underground personnel, but also works in accordance with regulatory authorities. Studio day-to-day management mine ventilation system is essential to achieve all objectives from the ventilation system. Ventilation control system used to ensure, measure and control quantity and quality air flow through the mine ventilation network. It consists of an iterative framework through ventilation management programs which mine ventilation section maintains ventilation system in accordance with regulatory authorities and company

policies. It consists of systematic documents that form standardized procedures and guidelines for system testing and provisioning corrective actions when an upset situation occurs, therefore safer and a more efficient system is maintained. Correct implementation ventilation management software provides significant benefits including increased operational efficiency, increased safety, increasing engineering efficiency, reducing equipment (fans, doors, regulators, channels, etc.) to reduce maintenance costs and energy expenses. Quality management allows mining operations to proactively implement mitigation techniques before underground environmental conditions become hazardous, thereby avoiding them. undesirable reactive practices. Here are the examples the paper demonstrates the direct benefits of ventilation control software.

Structure of the ventilation control program

A quality management program is defined as a means for organizations to meet performance expectations by providing offer quality assurance and control and optimization tools Although the management of system processes is improved, performance. A quality management program is supported by seven key requirements used to assess a company's ability to meet regulatory requirements as well as its internal policies: objective, policy, planning, implementation, measurement, review and improvement. The ventilation control system consists of: a set of documents describing the means of inspection and control of the mine ventilation system to ensure the system meets all regulatory and safety requirements. Five main document types make up the ventilation structure management system: standards and guidelines, code of practice, procedures, work instructions and guidelines (Picture 2). These documents provide guidance on the application of audit, inspection and remediation processes used to maintain mine ventilation systems works within compliance standards.

Picture 2. Scheme of the ventilation control system

Discussion

According to the results of optimization efforts, and beyond expectation. The original goal was to save energy Greater airflow control opens up new opportunities to bring control closer to design constraints. The The analysis of the fingerprint and ventilation system was very important first finding the appropriate scope of controls and tools to start the implementation. As the implementation went smoothly the scope and assumptions were all already in place from the start. The fact that the model is numerical and not analytical it is based on data and obtained using historical operations collected data or experiments involving step changes. This is new approach means that both the initial deployment of management, as well as maintenance of the lifetime model, along with the development of the mine, a relatively easy operation. Control is also proven stable operation for a long time without any need model recalibration. However, sooner or later, changes mines affect the optimization progress and therefore it is important to constantly monitor the result the right time to recalibrate the model.

Conclusions

Application of these dynamic empirical models to mine ventilation brings systems to optimize general air distribution several benefits. The mine owner or operator benefits not only from reduced running costs, but also from receiving optimized air flows that best suit the operation in the working environment. that place Despite the developing nature of the mine, there is the model maintains speed by optimizing air and fan continuous.

-> Combined tools and ease of use vary With advanced controls seamlessly integrated into the control system environment, the user can easily change the interface signal and adjusting constraints without additional knowledge or tools. Such as the result is the historically normal fate of model management; slowly deterioration and obsolescence of control effectiveness time does not occur in this case.

-> Defined workflows establish a shared waiting area and stable performance in the spotlight A method for developing a basic design capability and value proposition in fingerprint analysis is recommended. It is also part of the commonly used working method advanced management software in various applications. The the evaluation-implementation-sustainability cycle proves to work here too implementation. It is too early to draw a firm conclusion best determine when to take action on implementation of ventilation optimization is described in this article.

At the same time, it is clear that it is desirable to automatically monitor the operation of the control in order to save savings. evolves requires vigilance suitable for automatic monitoring and the ability to reason about results. down. Is this the result of a mining pattern change a recalibration of the scale thirsty model, malfunctioning equipment and sensors or other causes of suboptimal results, performance monitors should display accordingly. Also, continuous Monitoring is good for ventilation control programs in improving operational efficiency, improving safety, improving engineering efficiency, and assisting in the reduction process equipment (fans, doors, regulators, ducts, etc.) maintenance costs and reduces energy consumption. For such monitoring functions ventilation indicators are currently developing further.

→ Importance of different implementation layers in ventilation control in this example, the implementation of the control is located in the layer note that the optimization described here is also without control working paper, safe and stable ventilation function is stable by lower control layers. This shows that cloud-based optimization functions are a real possibility without compromising production stability. This in turn opens up new opportunities continues the actions using the ease of implementation and control technologies such as machine learning are examples.

The ventilation control software ensures mining operations an iterative process that can standardize daily ventilation practices, audit ventilation systems and ensure compliance with regulatory authorities and company policies. It provides effective tools for proper control and management of complex ventilation networks, resulting in significant safety, efficiency and economy mining benefits. In this article, the structure and ventilation control program implementation process is provided. The daily application of the ventilation management program ensures that the operation of the mine complies with all regulatory documents requirements and care for the health and safety of all employees work underground. Two job applications are submitted demonstrate the functionality of the management software and feasible safety, efficacy and economic benefit through mining operations.

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